

Compounds of Tungsten (VI) Chloride with Aminophenols, Aminobenzoic Acids, Nitroanilines, Amides, and Anilides

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Compounds of tungsten(VI) chloride with aminophenols, aminobenzoic acids, nitroanilines, amides, and anilides have been prepared, their properties studied, and structures discussed.

No work seems to have been done on the formation of compounds of tungsten(VI) chloride with aminophenols, aminobenzoic acids, nitroanilines, amides, and anilides. In earlier communications (this *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 588; this *issue*, p. 182) the action of tungsten(VI) chloride on some amines and heterocyclic bases was studied. The work has now been extended to study the action of these compounds on tungsten (VI) chloride in organic solvents.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Tungsten(VI) chloride was prepared as before (*loc. cit.*) and extracted with anhydrous CCl_4 . The organic solvents used were dehydrated and redistilled. The other chemicals used were of B.D.H. or Merck's 'extra pure' quality.

On mixing separately ethereal solutions of aminophenols, aminobenzoic acids, nitroanilines, amides, and anilides with tungsten(VI) chloride in CCl_4 , complex compounds separated immediately. The precipitate was filtered and washed with dry ether till free of the reactants, and finally dried in vacuum. In the case of urea, which is very sparingly soluble in ether, the compound was prepared by adding an excess of WCl_6 in CCl_4 to a suspension of urea in ether, and the mixture was left for 24 hours with frequent shaking. After the reaction was over, the supernatant liquid was decanted and the compound obtained was washed several times with dry ether and finally dried in vacuum. Tungsten, chlorine, and nitrogen were estimated as before (*loc. cit.*).

General Properties.—All the compounds are coloured and insoluble in common organic solvents, except ethanol in which these are sparingly soluble. These products are fairly stable in dry atmosphere, but when exposed to moist air, these absorb moisture and decompose.

TABLE I

Compounds of WCl_6 with nitroanilines, aminophenols, and aminobenzoic acids.

Compounds used.	Product.	Colour.	%Tungsten.		%Chlorine.		%Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. <i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	$[\text{W}(\text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2]\text{Cl}_6$	Yellowish brown	14.76	15.02	17.28	17.37	..	..
2. <i>m</i> - ..	Do	Light brown	15.10	15.02	17.40	17.37	..	..
3. <i>p</i> - ..	Do	Yellow	14.89	15.02	17.13	17.37	..	..
4. <i>o</i> -Aminophenol	$[\text{W}(\text{OH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2]\text{Cl}_6$	Dark brown	25.36	25.42	29.33	29.39	5.769	5.803
5. <i>m</i> - ..	Do	Grey	25.25	25.42	29.16	29.39	5.810	5.803
6. <i>p</i> - ..	Do	Grey	25.06	25.42	29.18	29.39	5.743	5.803
7. <i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	$\text{W}(\text{COOH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2\text{Cl}_6$	Brown	27.12	27.43	31.49	31.71	4.107	4.176
8. <i>p</i> -	Do	Light green	27.31	27.43	31.62	31.71	4.143	4.176

TABLE II
Compounds of WCl_6 with amides and anilides.

Amides or anilides.	Product.	Colour.	%Tungsten.		%Chlorine.		%Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. Urea	$[W\{(NH_2)_2CO\}_6]Cl_6$	Bluish grey	24.18	24.31	27.97	28.11	21.86	22.210
2. Acetamide	$[W(CH_3CO.NH_2)_6]Cl_6$	Greenish yellow	24.09	24.50	28.20	28.33	..	..
3. Benzamide	$W(C_6H_5CO.NH_2)_6Cl_6$	Blue	28.36	28.80	33.08	33.31	4.139	4.385
4. Acetanilide	$[W(CH_3CO.NHC_6H_5)_6]Cl_6$	Blue	15.32	15.24	17.49	17.63	6.936	6.963
5. <i>o</i> -Nitroacetanilide	$[W(NO_2.C_6H_4NH.COCH_3)_6]Cl_6$	Lemon-yellow	12.18	12.46	14.18	14.40	..	..
6. <i>p</i> -Aminoacetanilide	$[W(NH_2.C_6H_4NHCOCH_3)_6]Cl_6$	Light brown	14.12	14.19	16.26	16.40	..	..
7. Benzanilide	$W(C_6H_5CONHC_6H_5)_6Cl_6$	Greenish white	23.04	23.27	26.71	26.90	3.400	3.542

DISCUSSION

From the results it is evident that six molecules of nitroaniline combine with one molecule of tungsten (VI) chloride; the compounds obtained are similar to those obtained with aromatic primary amines (*loc. cit.*). It appears that the nitro group does not co-ordinate in presence of a strong donor group like $-NH_2$.

In the case of aminophenols only three molecules of aminophenol combine with one molecule of tungsten (VI) chloride, showing thereby the co-ordination of both $-NH_2$ and OH groups. The compounds formed are fairly stable.

It is interesting to note that only two molecules of aminobenzoic acids combine with one molecule of tungsten (VI) chloride and the compounds formed are more stable than those obtained with tertiary amines.

In the case of urea, acetamide, acetanilide, *o*-nitroacetanilide, and *p*-aminoacetanilide six molecules of each combine with one molecule of tungsten(VI) chloride and the compounds obtained are very stable. It appears that the carbonyl group present in them being very reactive and also the affinity of tungsten towards oxygen being very strong, the chlorine is readily displaced to the outer ring; the compound obtained with urea may be represented as: $[W\{CO(NH_2)_2\}_6]Cl_6$.

Only two molecules of benzamide or benzanilide evidently combine with one molecule of WCl_6 . The aromatic group in these molecules apparently offers steric hindrance and the carbonyl group becomes sufficiently weak to displace the chlorine to the outer ring.

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